

THE EFFECT OF TEAMWORK AND WORK DISCIPLINE IN IMPROVING TEACHER PRODUCTIVITY

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Received : 29 October 2025

Revised : 20 November 2025

Accepted : 15 December 2025

Published : 28 December 2025

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.54443/morfai.v6i2.4834>

Publish Link : <https://radjapublika.com/index.php/MORFAI/article/view/4834>

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of teamwork and work discipline as an important foundation in increasing teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu. The method used is quantitative with a population and sample of 30 people including the principal and teachers. The sampling technique is a saturated sampling approach. Data collection in this study was obtained through interviews and questionnaire distribution which were then processed using the SPSS ver. 25 application. The data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis. The results obtained state that: (1) partially teamwork has a positive and significant effect on increasing teacher productivity; (2) partially work discipline has a positive and significant effect on increasing teacher productivity; and (3) simultaneously there is a significant influence between teamwork and work discipline on teacher productivity;

Keywords: *Teamwork, Work Discipline, Productivity*

INTRODUCTION

One of the keys to improving an organization, be it a school or an agency, is inseparable from human resources, success in achieving predetermined goals is highly dependent on human resource productivity. The higher the productivity of human resources, the more quality work results in an efficient time and cost. Effective human resource management is key to improving a productive and harmonious work environment (Muktamar *et al.*, 2024). In the educational sphere, the presence of productive teachers is a key factor in efforts to improve the quality of education provided. One of the concrete results produced by a teacher is his ability to develop an educational curriculum and annual and semester evaluation systems, compile Learning Implementation Plans (RPP) for the subjects taught, and carry out the educational process, assessment, and analysis of educational outcomes. The main duties of a teacher are in accordance with Government Regulation No. 74 of 2008 concerning teachers, article 52 paragraph 1, namely teachers are professional educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing, and evaluating students in early childhood education, formal education, and secondary education. primary education, and secondary education (Devi *et al.*, 2023).

Since 2021, SMP Negeri 18 Palu has been a member of the School Mover Program, a school focused on holistically developing student learning outcomes by realizing the Pancasila Student Profile, encompassing cognitive (literacy and numeracy) and non-cognitive (character) competencies, starting with superior human resources (principals and teachers). The principal and teachers of the School Mover program disseminate information to other educational units. The School Mover Program aims to improve the quality of student learning and accelerate the school's progress by one or two stages within three academic years. Implementation of this program requires optimal work performance, thus encouraging each teacher to be more productive. One of the factors that influence productivity is teamwork. Essentially, teamwork involves good communication, collaboration, and coordination among team members to achieve common goals (Kinni *et al.*, 2024). Teamwork has the potential to improve work and productivity between various divisions through various diverse individual skills, which can be used as a powerful resource in achieving goals in schools. The quality of decisions and the level of creativity produced through teamwork are far better than those that can be provided by individuals working alone (Sihombing, 2024). Therefore, a deep understanding of the factors that influence team dynamics and productivity is crucial in the context of modern management (Hasanuddin *et al.*, 2024). Based on the results of interviews with the vice principal of curriculum, it was found that although most educators had made efforts to collaborate, educate, teach, guide, direct, train, assess, and evaluate students as well as adjustments to teaching modules or Learning Implementation Plans (RPP) at that

time were still relatively new and generally obtained through online coaching activities. This condition makes the need for collaboration between teachers increasingly important, especially to deepen understanding and enrich information related to the preparation of teaching modules that comply with the provisions of the School Mover Program. In addition to teamwork, productivity certainly requires discipline from each member to ensure sustainable collaboration among teachers. Good work discipline significantly enhances the organization's goals and ensures order and smooth task execution (Hartina *et al.*, 2021). Good work discipline can help teachers work efficiently and effectively, thereby increasing teacher productivity (Syiva *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 1
Summary of Teacher Absences at SMP Negeri 18 Palu in 2024

Source: Secondary Data (2025)

Teacher work discipline at SMP Negeri 18 Palu can be seen in the diagram above, which shows a decline in teacher absence data from January to December 2024. This decline in absences is in line with the results of interviews conducted, which revealed that several lesson hours were not implemented properly, resulting in a situation where the time allocated for learning activities was not optimally utilized. This phenomenon reflects that although regulations regarding attendance and teaching hours have been established by the school, their implementation has not been fully effective for all teachers. This phenomenon certainly attracts attention to conduct research on the synergy between teamwork and work discipline in improving teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Productivity

Productivity is a measure of productive efficiency. It is a comparison between output and input. Input is often limited to labor, while output is measured in physical units, form, and value (Qomariah, 2020). Another definition states that productivity is a comparison of the quality and quantity of workers within a certain time period in order to achieve efficient and effective results or work performance according to the resources used (Sukardi *et al.*, 2024). According to Qomariah (2020:81) to measure productivity, an indicator is needed, namely as follows:

- Abilities that match the skills they possess and their professionalism in working.
- Increase the results that can be felt by both those who do the work and those who enjoy the results of the work.
- Work enthusiasm is the teacher's enthusiasm to provide better results than before.
- Self-development, self-development can be done by looking at the challenges and hopes of what will be faced.
- Quality as a result of work that can show the quality of a teacher's work.
- Efficiency, the comparison between the results achieved and the total resources used.

Teamwork

Collaboration in the educational context has significant potential to maximize human resources and achieve educational goals more effectively (Triwijayanti *et al.*, 2022). In a school environment, teamwork means efficient collaboration and interaction between various elements, such as school leaders, teachers, staff, parents, and the surrounding community (Baharun, 2023). According to Pratama *et al.*, (2022:6) to measure teamwork, an indicator is needed, including the following:

- a. Commitment among team members serves to align the perception that achieving shared goals is a responsibility that must be carried out by all team members with full commitment and responsibility.
- b. Effective communication carried out by each team member can be received well or equally by the communicator and the communicant, so that there are no misperceptions that hinder the interpretation of the goals of the team in which the member is located.
- c. Trust in fellow team members provides positive motivation for each member within the function, thus having a positive impact on accelerating the team's achievement of predetermined goals.
- d. Contribution, meaning the quality of cooperation within a team is determined by, among other things, the team's contribution to the scientific field and experience that corresponds to the tasks assigned by the school.
- e. Clear goals and having targets for achievement or expected measurable results are one of the aspects that determine the success of teamwork when the work is carried out.

Work Discipline

Work discipline is an attitude, behavior, and actions that are in accordance with both written and unwritten regulations, and if violated there will be sanctions for the violation (Khaeruman *et al.*, 2021). Work discipline is a mental attitude reflected in individual and group actions of compliance and obedience to the regulations set to strengthen organizational guidelines (Armansyah *et al.*, 2020).

According to Khaeruman *et al.*, (2021:22) there are several components used as indicators in measuring work discipline, such as:

- a. The level of absence is one of the benchmarks for determining the level of employee discipline. The higher the frequency of attendance or the lower the level of absence, the higher the employee's work discipline.
- b. Complying with regulations, meaning that teachers who comply with work regulations will not neglect work procedures and will always follow the work guidelines set by the school, thus creating comfort and smoothness in work.
- c. Effective use of time, the working time given by the school is expected to be utilized as well as possible by individuals to achieve the targets given by the school to individuals without wasting too much of the available time.
- d. Responsibility is the teacher's commitment and obligation to complete a task well and within the specified time.

Framework of Thought

Figure 2.
Conceptual Framework of Research

Hypothesis

- H₁ : Teamwork and work discipline simultaneously have a significant influence on increasing teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu.
- H₂ : Teamwork has a significant partial effect in increasing teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu
- H₃ : Work discipline has a partial significant effect on increasing teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at SMP Negeri 18 Palu using a quantitative approach. Data collection techniques in this study were observation, interviews, and using a questionnaire list, which could be filled out directly by respondents. The population in this study was the principal and several teachers at the research location, totaling 30. The sampling technique used a saturated sampling approach. Data analysis techniques consisted of instrument testing by conducting data validity and reliability tests. Then, classical assumption tests (normality test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test). Then, hypothesis testing (t-test and f-test), followed by statistical analysis testing (multiple linear regression analysis test, and R² determination coefficient test) using SPSS software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Instrument Testing

Before being distributed to research objects, the instrument to be used in this research was first tested at SMP Negeri 20 Palu to test its validity and reliability.

a. Validity Test

The results of the validity test of this study show that for each statement item, the calculated r-value for each variable is ≥ 0.305, meaning the calculated r-value > r-table (0.3) so that the instrument in this study is declared valid.

b. Reliability Test

The results of the reliability test of this study show that the Cronbach's alpha coefficient for each variable is ≥ 0.875, meaning that the Cronbach's alpha value is > standard error (0.6), so that the instrument in this study is declared reliable or has good measurement consistency so that it can be used on relatively the same objects.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 1
Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	.936	11,005		.085	.933		
Teamwork	.411	.169	.334	2,429	.022	.783	1,277
Work Discipline	.674	.165	.561	4,079	.000	.783	1,277

a. Dependent Variable: Productivity
Source: SPSS Output Results Ver. 25

Based on the results of this study, the following multiple linear regression equation model was obtained:

$$Y = 0.936 + 0.411 X1 + 0.674 X2 + 0.05$$

- a. The constant value of 0.936 means that if the teamwork and work discipline variables are 0, the productivity level of teachers at SMP Negeri 18 Palu is 93.6%.
- b. The teamwork regression coefficient value (X1) is 0.411, meaning that every one percent change in teamwork has an impact on increasing the productivity of teachers at SMP Negeri 18 Palu by 41.1%, assuming that work discipline remains the same.
- c. The work discipline coefficient value (X2) is 0.674, meaning that every one percent change in work discipline has an impact on increasing the productivity of teachers at SMP Negeri 18 Palu by 67.4%, assuming teamwork remains the same.

Hypothesis Testing

a. Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 2
Results of the Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.775 ^a	.600	.571	3,462
a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Discipline, Teamwork				
b. Dependent Variable: Productivity				

Source: SPSS Output Results Ver. 25

Adjusted R Square value in the table above, the value is 0.571. This means that 57.1% of productivity in this study was influenced by teamwork and work discipline. The remaining 42.9% was influenced by variables outside the regression model.

b. ANOVA Significance Test (F Statistic Test)

Table 3
F Statistical Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	485,930	2	242,965	20,274	.000 ^b
	Residual	323,570	27	11,984		
	Total	809,500	29			
a. Dependent Variable: Productivity						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Work Discipline, Teamwork						

Source: SPSS Output Results Ver. 25

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the significance level of the f statistical test shows a result of sig. $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that teamwork (X1) and work discipline (X2) simultaneously have a significant effect in increasing the productivity (Y) of teachers at SMP Negeri 18 Palu.

d. Individual Parameter Test (t-Statistic Test)

Table 4
t-Statistic Test

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.936	11,005		.085	.933		
	Teamwork	.411	.169	.334	2,429	.022	.783	1,277
	Work Discipline	.674	.165	.561	4,079	.000	.783	1,277
a. Dependent Variable: Productivity								

Source: SPSS Output Results Ver. 25

Based on the table above, the partial influence of each independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) can be seen as follows:

- a. The significance level of teamwork (X1) shows a value of sig. $0.02 < 0.05$ so that H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This means that teamwork partially has a positive and significant effect in increasing the productivity of teachers at SMP Negeri 18 Palu with a contribution of 0.334 or 33.4%.
- b. The significance level of work discipline (X2) shows a value of sig. $0.00 < 0.05$ so that H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This means that work discipline partially has a positive and significant effect in increasing the productivity of teachers at SMP Negeri 18 Palu with a contribution of 0.561 or 56.1%.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Teamwork and Work Discipline in Increasing Teacher Productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu

Based on the results of the F statistical test analysis, it shows that the level of significance obtained is sig. $0.000 < 0.05$, meaning that the results obtained are H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted so that it can be concluded that teamwork and work discipline simultaneously have a significant effect in increasing the productivity of teachers at SMP Negeri 18 Palu. The results of this analysis indicate that the current level of teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu is 93.6% and 57.1% is influenced by teamwork and work discipline, while the rest is influenced by other variables outside the regression model. The results of this study are supported by Fidianingsih *et al.*, (2023) that there is a significant influence that occurs between work discipline, teamwork and workload on direct labor productivity at PT. Wonojati Wijoyo Kediri.

The results of this study indicate that teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu is influenced by work discipline and teamwork. This is due to the efforts of teachers in forming teamwork in the school environment through the Teacher Working Group which is routinely held once a week. In addition, the orientation of schools that have recently entered the School Mover Program certainly presents a new challenge for teachers in adjusting modules or Learning Implementation Plans (RPP) which are still relatively new so that many of the teachers collaborate not only in the work environment, but even to the scope of teachers between schools to share information on module preparation methods according to the specified results. In the process of increasing productivity, of course, good teacher discipline is also needed. The results of the analysis show that work discipline at SMP Negeri 18 Palu has been implemented very well through efforts to consistently maintain excellent teacher attendance, optimized use of teaching time and use of free time to complete pending tasks as well as the imposition of sanctions on teachers who lack discipline in the form of warning letters and consolidation by the principal regarding issues of lateness to absence. This certainly supports the increase in teacher productivity considering the orientation of the Driving School which focuses on improving the quality of student learning to accelerate the school to move 1-2 stages further, so that teachers are required to be more productive in improving the achievement of results in accordance with the provisions that have been set.

The Influence of Teamwork in Increasing Teacher Productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu

Based on the results of the t-statistic test in this study, a significance level of sig. $0.02 < 0.05$ was obtained, meaning that H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted, so the results of the analysis showed that teamwork partially had a positive and significant effect on increasing the productivity of teachers at SMP Negeri 18 Palu, meaning that the more the teamwork of teachers in the environment of SMP Negeri 18 Palu, the teacher productivity would also increase. The results of this study are supported by Prasista *et al.*, (2025) that partially there was a significant influence that occurred in teamwork on productivity at Ndalem Manten Wedding Organizer. The analysis in this study shows that the implementation of teamwork in SMP Negeri 18 Palu has been very well attempted because it is based on clear goals and the unity of teachers' perspectives in implementing the vision and mission that increasingly increases teacher motivation in working to achieve good performance. In addition to clear goals, teamwork in SMP Negeri 18 Palu is also based on high trust, both reliable colleagues, credible work results as well as support from other colleagues that further increase the sense of trust to work together well. This can also be seen from the commitment of teachers in carrying out joint tasks and doing problem solving when encountering difficulties. In addition, the role of teachers in improving work performance and actively participating in providing ideas or concepts as evaluation materials also contributes to realizing the shared vision and mission that is built through open information that is easy to understand and the opportunity for employees to convey aspirations as considerations so as to form effective communication in collaboration.

The Influence of Work Discipline in Increasing Teacher Productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu

Based on the results of the t-statistic test in this study, the significance level obtained was sig. $0.00 < 0.05$, meaning that H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. This shows that partially work discipline has a positive and

significant effect on increasing teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu, meaning that an increase in work discipline will be directly proportional to an increase in teacher productivity in SMP Negeri 18 Palu. The results of this study are supported by Bahtiar & Aprianti (2023) that there is a significant influence that occurs in work discipline on employee productivity at the Department of Industry and Trade in Bima Regency. The analysis in this study shows that teacher work discipline at SMP Negeri 18 Palu has an impact on increasing teacher productivity. The phenomenon of decreasing teacher absenteeism in the background directly impacts the effectiveness of poorly implemented class hours which affect teacher achievement in realizing school acceleration to be 1-2 stages more advanced than other schools. At SMP Negeri 18 Palu, the Principal has attempted to implement sanctions in the form of Warning Letters (SP) to undisciplined teachers, thus requiring teachers to maintain consistent attendance and ensure attendance data is input properly. In addition, in complying with applicable regulations, teachers strive to carry out their work in accordance with established standards, obey applicable rules and maintain ethics as a teacher should in the school environment. The school also implements monitoring carried out by administrative staff to ensure that class hours have been carried out properly, and carries out productive activities by utilizing free time to complete unfinished tasks and being responsible for student learning outcomes, striving to complete tasks on time and being willing to accept the consequences of the work results. This is done to maximize the achievement of work results to support the objectives of the School Mover Program.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis of the results and discussions that have been carried out, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Teamwork and work discipline simultaneously have a significant influence in increasing teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu.
2. Teamwork partially has a positive and significant effect on increasing teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu.
3. Work discipline has a partial positive and significant effect on increasing teacher productivity at SMP Negeri 18 Palu.

Suggestion

1. Teachers are advised to maintain consistency in completing assignments according to the established schedule to support optimal productivity.
2. Each teacher is expected to build mutual trust in order to form a cooperative attitude that relies on each other to achieve maximum work performance.
3. It is hoped that teachers will continue to improve their abilities in developing more innovative teaching materials that are appropriate to students' needs based on the applicable curriculum.
4. It is recommended that future researchers add other variables that have the potential to enhance teacher productivity, such as leadership, motivation, and job satisfaction.

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